

Role of Left-Wing Political Parties in Pakistan: A Case of Pakistan People's Party

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Abstract

In electoral and authoritarian democracies, political parties are considered essential for the system. Pakistan emerged as an ideological state. After a few years of its emergence, liberal and secular parties tried their best to engage in politics compared to the traditional parties. In Pakistan, leftist parties such as the Pakistan Communist Party, NAP, ANP, PPP, and MQM participated in electoral politics without using religious cover. These parties were based on a socio-economic manifesto and propagated equal socio-economic rights for the people, isolating the role of religion in politics. The People's party, as a leftist party, faced numerous challenges from its formation to its evolution. This paper explores and highlights the historical evolution of the Pakistan People's Party.

Keywords: Pakistan, Politics, Parties, elections, Leftist, People's Party Historical,

Discussion

Socialism has great influences in backward countries, while in Pakistan socialist moments have taken different forms as a counterpart to political conservatism, from the groups like the Struggle, Lal Salam which is the Pakistani section of the International Marxist Tendency, to the Stalinist group like Communist Party through to the reformist electoral project enshrined in the birth of the Pakistan People's Party (PPP). In a democratic political system, political parties have a status nearly equivalent to the blood flowing through the human body. Just as the health of the human body depends on blood, the success and future of the democratic system depend on the efficiency, organization, and leadership of political parties. That is why political experts consider the existence of political parties indispensable for the success of modern democracy. Munro says, "Government by independent political parties is

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truly another name for democratic government. A political party with shared ideas, a unified manifesto, and a commitment to serving the country and the nation after gaining power are indeed links in the same chain." The number of political parties in Pakistan is more than one hundred; however, it is difficult to "accuse" most of them of being a political party and then a political party with a national-level identity and the ability to influence the country's politics. Parties are non-existent.

After the emergence of Pakistan, Pakistan Communist Party was popular and it formed government in East Pakistan with the support of Awami League. The party was also supported by the rural and lower class due to the open stance of socio-economic issues.¹ The class struggle reached its limit when members of PML and the Communist Party scuffled violently with East-Pakistani police in 1958. The government responded by dismissing the government of the Communist Party in East Pakistan and arresting 1,000 members of the Communist Party in West Pakistan, eventually banning the Communist Party there as well.² According to the Chief Economist of the Planning Commission, Dr. Mahbub-ul-Haq, by 1968 "22 industrial family groups had come to dominate the economic and financial life-cycle of Pakistan and that they controlled about two-thirds of industrial assets, 80% of banking and 79% of insurance assets in the industrial domain." [15] Further, President Khan's peaceful compromise with India in 1965 to end the Indo-Pakistani War created large scale disapproval from civil society.³ Among the current political parties, the People's Party claims to be the largest and federal party; The PPP's manifesto called, titled "Islam is our Religion; Democracy is our Politics; Socialism is our Economy; Power Lies with the People", was written by Bengali communist J. A. Rahim, and first issued on 9 December 1967⁴, the background of its evolutionary history is as follows.

The Awami National Party (ANP) was founded in 1986 with a manifesto based on the ideology of Khan Abdul Ghaffar Khan. Khan Abdul Ghaffar, also known as "Bacha Khan," was a staunch advocate of provincial autonomy and non-violence. ANP actually originated from within the National Awami Party (NAP). The founder of the Pakistan People's Party (PPP), Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, accused ANP leader Wali Khan of involvement in the assassination of PPP sympathizer Hayat Mohammad Khan Sherpao and subsequently arrested him, imposing restrictions on the party. During Zia-ul-Haq's regime, Wali Khan was released, and he went on to establish ANP. Despite distancing itself from the core principles of Marxism, which were initially embraced by the NAP, ANP has remained active. ANP accepts the role of the open market in economic affairs and relies more on government funds than on creating employment opportunities. ANP is a nationalist party with a strong focus on Pashtun rights, advocating for equal rights for all citizens regardless of race, color, or gender. While the party has consistently called for peace in the country, it has also faced allegations of involvement in ethnic clashes in Karachi with the Muttahida Qaumi Movement (MQM). It is important to note that in Karachi, the MQM and ANP and PPP are considered major political parties.

Political Alignment

ANP, despite its secular ideology, has formed political alliances with religious groups such as the Jamiat Ulema-e-Islam Fazlur Rehman Group (JUI-F).

Stronghold

ANP's stronghold lies in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Karachi, particularly areas with a significant Pashtun population.

Political Agenda

ANP has outlined its political agenda with respect to several key issues:

1. Renaming Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to "ANP": ANP has proposed a new name for Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, suggesting it be called "ANP."
2. Position on Critical Matters: ANP has taken a stance on important issues, including demanding a separate province comprising regions with a Pashtun majority population, following the merger of the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) into Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.
3. Opposition to Military Interference in Administrative Affairs: ANP strongly opposes military intervention in administrative matters and calls for allocating budgetary funds for the betterment and welfare of the public.
4. Support for Provincial Autonomy and the 18th Amendment: ANP is a staunch supporter of provincial autonomy and the implementation of the 18th Amendment. The party believes that government officials should seek permission from the provincial government before appointing officers from other provinces.
5. Commitment to the Democratic System: ANP emphasizes the importance of upholding the democratic system and advocates for friendly relations with neighboring countries like India and Afghanistan, while refraining from interfering in the internal affairs of any country.

Elections 2002

The party's performance in the 2002 elections was extremely disappointing. However, political analysts claimed that electoral fraud had been committed in favor of religious groups, resulting in significantly fewer votes for the secular party.

Elections 2008

ANP not only secured 15 seats in the National Assembly but also emerged as the largest political party in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, leading to the formation of the government.

Elections 2013

In comparison to the 2008 elections, ANP's performance in the 2013 elections was extremely disappointing. ANP won only 2 seats in the National Assembly in the 2013 elections, with Ghulam Ahmad Bilour and Amir Haider Khan emerging victorious in general constituencies. In the 2008 elections in Pakistan, Pakistan People's Party (PPP) and Awami National Party (ANP) had formed the government in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, where ANP members were well represented. However, in the 2013 elections, the party suffered a significant decline in its vote bank, and this trend continued in the 2018 elections, with further reductions in their electoral support.

Conflicts

Former President General Pervez Musharraf imposed martial law in 1999, and the issue of a political alliance with Pervez Musharraf caused a rift within ANP, led by its chief, Asfandiyar Wali Khan. This disagreement escalated, leading him to eventually break away from the party. Asfandiyar Wali Khan was initially in favor of participating in the political alliance. Later on, the party's leadership was entrusted to the son of Wali Khan, Asfandiyar Wali Khan, and then Asfandiyar Wali Khan himself rejoined the party. According to media reports, there were tensions among ANP leaders and workers, especially among female workers. This was attributed to the party's decision to award tickets for the 2018 elections to old faces rather than new ones. Later, disgruntled members of ANP's provincial assembly joined the Pakistan People's Party (PPP).

Terrorism Victims

Due to their clear stance against terrorism, ANP leaders have been the target of multiple attacks. Several ANP workers have sacrificed their lives in attacks. The senior leader of the party, Haroon Bilour, the son of Bashir Bilour, was killed in a suicide attack during an election campaign event on July 10, 2018. In this attack, more than 20 individuals lost their lives, with the majority being party workers. Another senior leader of the party and member of the provincial assembly, Bashir Ahmed Bilour, was killed in a suicide attack in 2012, which was claimed by the Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP). In a targeted attack, Bashir Ahmed Bilour lost his life along with his secretary, a police officer, and six others in 2008. In 2010, his sister, Dr. Gulalai, was injured in another attack. Although there has been a significant reduction in terrorist activities in the country following military operations, those who speak out against terrorism still face threats to their lives. According to ANP, their leaders have been consistently facing security threats. However, following the directives of the Chief Justice of Pakistan, ANP Chief Asfandiyar Wali Khan, General Secretary Mian Iftikhar Hussain, and other politicians, police officers, and judges have had their security restored.

Party Manifesto

Although ANP has claimed that they will participate in the elections of the new constitution, their website still contains the old manifesto published in 2013. The manifesto contains vague positions on various issues. While ANP voters know "what" the party intends, there is no clarity on "how" these intentions will be fulfilled.

Regarding women's rights, ANP's manifesto promises an increase in the number of reserved seats for women and minorities and pledges equal rights for all citizens regardless of religion, gender, or language.

Despite these promises in the manifesto, ANP's female workers have complained that they were unable to submit their nomination papers due to an increase in ticket fees imposed by the party leadership. On the other hand, the party claims that the purpose of the fee increase is to improve funds.

The manifesto states that funds will be established for the families of martyrs.

The manifesto strongly supports provincial autonomy.

Pashtun Culture

The party's manifesto promises the creation of funds for women, families affected by terrorism, and other needy households, but it doesn't focus much on creating employment opportunities.

The manifesto emphasizes domestic industry and business development.

Although the party's manifesto mentions several promises, ANP has faced challenges in implementing its policies effectively in various matters.

Pakistan People's Party

After the creation of Pakistan, unlike the parties with Islamist ideas, some political parties inspired by communism and Marxist philosophy started their political life. One of them was the Pakistan Communist Party, which was prominent. After the party was banned, the National Awami Party came into existence in 1957, which later became the Awami National Party. But the most important was the Awami League. After the Tashkent accord, Bhutto followed socialist ideals and started trying to form a new party, and finally, on November 30, 1967, another left-wing party came into being. The People's Party started participating in electoral politics from 1970 and struggled against the perceived right-wing parties.

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto was an important, extraordinary talent, and controversial political figure of his era. He was a member and general secretary of Ayub Khan's Convention Muslim League. In the beginning, he tried to capture it by forming a forward block in the Convention Muslim League and then by becoming a member of the Council Muslim League; he also considered the possibility of uniting the factions of the Muslim League. He resigned from his political guardian Ayub Khan's cabinet in 1966 after disagreements over the Tashkent Agreement and, overcome by a sense of revenge, began to criticize him. Bhutto even visited East Pakistan in November 1966 to express support for Mujibur Rahman's six-point program, even though as foreign minister he had denounced the same scheme of autonomy as anti-national.

According to Lawrence Ziring, "Bhutto knew that Ayub would eventually resign from his post, so he bowed down to the man he had employed for eight years." Later he decided to form a political party because he was not satisfied with any other political party, its leadership, manifesto, and performance. He wanted to create a political party that could be a vehicle for the propagation of Jawan's personal philosophy and which had no antecedents or suffixes of past events and personalities. He announced the formation of People's Party in October 1967. From November 30 to December 1, 1967, a national convention was held under the leadership of Bhutto at the residence of Dr. Mubashir Hasan in Lahore. JA Rahim, Abdul Hafeez Pirzada, Sheikh Abdul Rasheed, Yahya Bakhtiar, Meraj Mohammad Khan, Taj Mohammad Langah, Mumtaz Bhutto, Mahmood Ali Kasuri, Hanif Ramey, Hayat Mohammad Khan Sherpao, Ghulam Mustafa Khar, Mukhtar Rana, Khurshid Hasan Mir, Comrades Ghulam Muhammad, Hamid Sarfraz, Malik Naveed Ahmed, Ahmad Khan, etc., joined it. On December 16, 1967, the party was formally formed at the residence of Mir Rasool Bakhsh Talpur, the leader of the opposition, in Hyderabad. The party slogan "Islam is our religion, democracy is our politics, socialism is our economy and the source of people's power" reflected the public thinking. This concept captivated people from the common man to the intellectuals, and people who were disappointed with the Ayub government also started looking towards the People's Party. Bhutto was arrested in November 1968. From then until March 1969, Bhutto's

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charismatic leadership organized the popular uprising against his former mentor and made the party more popular. Ayub ordered Bhutto's release so that he could engage in serious negotiations, but PPP leaders were hesitant about Bhutto's meeting with the president, which would strengthen Ayub's hands and prolong his rule. On March 25, 1969, the resignation of Ayub and the handing over of power to General Yahya Khan were announced.

The Pakistan People's Party is the second oldest political party in Pakistan, and it has faced many ups and downs since 1967. The General Secretary of Conventional ML and former Pakistan's Foreign Minister Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto bid farewell to President Ayub Khan's government on June 17, 1966, after eight years of friendship due to serious concerns over the Tashkent Agreement as a result of the September 1965 war. When he left for Karachi by train from the capital, he was greeted with applause by the people at every station, which gave Bhutto an idea of his popular popularity. Mr. Bhutto had become a national hero by virtue of his unparalleled performance in various ministries in the Ayub government, and now he became the nation's voice against an incompetent dictatorial regime. In such a situation, he had decided to participate in practical politics. According to Justice Javed Iqbal, Ms. Fatima Jinnah wanted to include Bhutto in her party, the Council Muslim League, but Bhutto had decided to form his own political party. Earlier in his early days, his father was keen to join Bhutto's Awami League, but the party never gained traction in West Pakistan.

On November 30, 1967, the People's Party was established in Lahore, with Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto elected as its chairman. The motto of this people-friendly political party with socialist ideals was Roti, Kapra, and Makan ("Bread, Cloth, and House"), while the basic manifesto was:

Islam is our religion

Democracy is our politics

The source of power is the people

Socialism is our economy

Due to floods, the polling dates for the National Assembly were fixed on December 7 and for the provincial assembly on December 17. PPP did not field any candidate from East Pakistan for the National Assembly, while it fielded 119 candidates in West Pakistan. During the election campaign, Bhutto relied on students, lawyers, and groups belonging to certain sectors who were at the forefront of the movement against the Ayub regime. The People's Party had the support of organized labor movements like Bashir Bakhtiar's Pakistan Labor Party, as well as the support of the Pakistan Press Workers Union, Tanga and Taxi Drivers Unions. The reason for PPP's popularity in the election campaign was its catchy slogan "Roti Kapra Aur Makan". According to the election results, the People's Party defeated the government-backed Qayyum League and religious parties, won a significant victory, and emerged as the second-largest majority party in the National Assembly, winning 81 out of 138 seats in West Pakistan. Later, by adding women and other seats, its number of seats became 88. More success was achieved in Punjab where 62 seats were won. The remaining seats except one went to Sindh. Although it was the majority party in West Pakistan, it got only 1/5 percent of the votes cast for the National Assembly.

Soon, the People's Party became the most popular political party in West Pakistan, but it was completely unpopular in East Pakistan, where Bengali nationalism was at its peak. In the general elections held in 1970, the People's Party had great success in West Pakistan in comparison to the religious and ideological parties. He was also in power after just one year

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due to the East Pakistan tragedy. Bhutto's People's Party was the only political party that had its roots in the people. About two years after the 1970 elections and about fourteen years of general democracy, the generals were ready to hand over power to Bhutto, the leader of the People's Party. In the words of the eminent intellectual Hamza Alvi, "The irony is that even though Bhutto was the leader of the majority party in (West) Pakistan, he did not come to power through the democratic process, but the defeated army removed him from the post of ruler." What did On December 20, 1971, the army appointed Bhutto as the President. Along with the President, Bhutto was also assigned the post of Chief Martial Law Administrator. These two positions were previously held by General Yahya.

For the first time in the country's history, a unified constitution was created and implemented. Pakistan's nuclear program started. Pakistan Steel Mill and Heavy Industries Taxila were established. The second Islamic summit in Lahore was organized. After the 1971 war, 90,000 soldiers were released from Indian captivity. During his tenure, a military operation took place in Balochistan, the NEP governments ended, and many opponents of Bhutto, including Mufti Mahmood and Khan Abdul Wali Khan, were imprisoned. Due to these actions, Bhutto also became a controversial figure. But even today, his opponents believe that as much work as he did in five years, the military or political leaders who came after him could not do it in ten years. After the removal of martial law, political parties did not get power for as long as the military rulers were in power.⁵ On January 7, 1977, it was announced that elections would be held in 2 months. Bhutto appointed Rafi Raza as the manager of his election campaign and decided to hold the elections in June 1976. The People's Party won a landslide victory, but the National Alliance took to the streets with allegations of rigging. However, Bhutto preferred to cling to power despite all the pressure. According to Lawrence Ziring, Bhutto was responsible for unleashing oppressive forces in Pakistani society, tearing the nation apart for personal gain, destroying the national economy, and forcing the country's best minds and hard-working people to leave. Allegations were made. It was widely felt that the same man who was entrusted with the task of healing the wounds of the terrible civil war would also ruin baby Pakistan if given the chance. Fate once again got busy and brought Ziaul Haq in Bhutto's place. "⁶ Bhutto was hanged on April 4, 1979. As it happened, it victimized Bhutto, and the public sympathized with him, as the army was punishing him for changing the political climate of the country. He became a symbol of crushed popular rights, so Bhutto's assassination was taken to mean that the army and the bureaucracy were responsible for the failure of Bhutto's socialist program and the end of democracy. Bhutto became the Peron of Pakistan. Iain Talbot believes that "Bhutto's supporters compare him to Chile's Salvador Allende, while his critics compare him to Argentina's Juan Perón."⁷

After Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's execution, his daughter Benazir Bhutto took over the reins of the party. During Ziaul Haq's martial law, many of her father's close associates left his side, including Ghulam Mustafa Jatoi, Mumtaz Bhutto, Ghulam Mustafa Khar, Dr. Mubasher Hassan, Dr. Ghulam Hussain, Abdul Hafeez Pirzada, etc.

After Tu's death, Begum Nusrat Bhutto took over the leadership of the People's Party, and Benazir became the co-chairperson. Zia defied the government and endured the hardships of imprisonment. On August 24, 1985, when Benazir came from England for the funeral of her brother Shahnawaz, the enthusiasm of the workers proved that the popularity of the party was established. She went back in November. The policy Zia laid down for non-partisan

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elections in 1985 was, according to Time magazine, "no political campaign, no issue, no stand, no debate on national issues." Despite this, Benazir was ready to jump into the fray, but the MRD decided not to participate in the elections as per Zia's rules.⁸

Anti-Bhutto forces tried hard to split the party but failed. This process started immediately after the fall of Bhutto in 1977 when the Progressive People's Party was formed in 1977 by Maulana Kausar Niazi. The National People's Party of Ghulam Mustafa Jatoi, the groups of Ghanwa Bhutto and Aftab Sherpao, and the People's Party Parliamentarians were formed during Musharraf's tenure, from which the People's Party Patriot under the leadership of Faisal Saleh Hayat was divided.

However, after the death of Zia-ul-Haq in an air crash, efforts to block his path by forming an Islamic democratic alliance under the auspices of the state failed miserably. When Benazir decided to return after a two-year self-imposed exile, she received a warm welcome on her arrival in Lahore from London. Seeing the crowd, Benazir had said with exaggeration that "we could have snatched power on the same day, but the crowd was in a mood of joy rather than violence." After returning home, Benazir criticized Zia by avoiding the Junejo government. To appease the powerful elements in power, Benazir declared: "I have not come to take revenge." As soon as Benazir returned home, conflicts broke out in the party. First, Ghulam Mustafa Jatoi, who headed the party in the absence of the Bhutto women, defected. According to him, Benazir wanted to get rid of all the "uncles" and take over the leadership herself. Among the uncles left behind was the real uncle Mumtaz Bhutto. He believed that the People's Party is so dependent on the votes of Punjab that it cannot look after the interests of Sindh. Benazir also faced a challenge from the Left. In 1988, the People's Party won with an overwhelming majority, and Benazir Bhutto became the first female Prime Minister of the Islamic world. But her government was not allowed to complete the term. When the President dismissed the government of the People's Party on August 16, 1990, there was no reaction from any part of America. If a general analysis is done, it can be said that at that time, the ruling Republican Party did not understand that most of Benazir's supporters and advisers had relations with the Democratic Party. Ghulam Ishaq Khan appointed former PPP chief and National People's Party chief Ghulam Mustafa Jatoi as caretaker prime minister. However, Benazir remained in the field of politics, but the president did not dismiss her because she would win again in the elections held three months later, so when the results of the elections were revealed, IJI got 105 seats while PPP, instead of the first 93, now it got only 45 seats.

In the elections of 1993, her party won again with a majority, and she was elected Prime Minister for the second time. PPP got 86 seats, and the Muslim League got 72 seats. After being in opposition for 3 years, Benazir Bhutto again became the Prime Minister and took oath on 19th October to heal the wounds inflicted on the country in the political conflict and to start the era of reconciliation. This time Benazir and the People's Party faced a challenge from their own home and family in the form of her brother Murtaza Bhutto. He considered himself the true heir of his father, and his mother Nusrat Bhutto was with him. In the background of this conflict, her political opponents also intensified their attacks. Benazir started a series of ex-servicemen and associates of Zia-ul-Haq, the main example of which was the appointment of General (ret'd) Saro Pak Khan as the Governor of Punjab. Murtaza Bhutto and her mother Nusrat Bhutto formed another PPP and recalled that her father had made her mother chairperson for life. The political game has now become a matter of life and

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death through lust for power. Bhutto's second son also sacrificed himself for power. In 1995, nearly 2,000 people were killed in Karachi alone. In short, the People's Party repeated the disappointments for the people in the second term of Benazir. The organization of the party continued to weaken. The situation reached such a level that on September 21, 1996, Prime Minister's brother Murtaza Bhutto was killed. In view of the various circumstances, the long-time worker of the People's Party and the elected president Farooq Laghari established a caretaker government by dissolving the Benazir government and the assemblies on the night of November 5, 1996, and appointed the 80-year-old Malik Meraj Khalid, a founding member of the PPP, as the prime minister. In March 1999, the party elected him president for life. Even in the special results of the special elections of 2002, the People's Party could not play a major role without a captain. Among those who succeeded, seasonal birds formed a forward block and took the name Patriot. He won with the party ticket, but after the victory, there was a fight. This damaged the party and its image. She was killed in a suicide attack in Rawalpindi on December 27, 2007, during the election. Bilawal Zardari became Bilawal Bhutto Zardari and appointed Chairman of PPP while Asif Ali Zardari selected Co-Chairman of PPP. In 2008, PPP won the election and Yousaf Raza Gilani appointed Prime Minister. Asif Zardari as President. But he was disqualified due to the verdict of the Supreme Court, and Raja Pervaz Ashraf completed the tenure of the PPP government.⁹

In such a situation, her husband Asif Ali Zardari took over the leadership of the party, and when he assumed power after the elections of February 2008, many people were also angry with him. Initially, Makhdoom Amin Fahim was unhappy, but later he took the ministry. Mian Raza Rabbani was angry at not being made Senate Chairman but continued to perform important responsibilities, including the amendment of the constitution and chairmanship of the National Security Committee of the Parliament. Aitzaz Ahsan distanced himself from the party leadership on the question of the restoration of judges but later played the role of a bridge between the government and the judiciary.

As far as the People's Party is concerned, there is no doubt that it has not been able to overcome the problems of governance, inflation, corruption, poverty, and unemployment, and has not fulfilled the expectations of the people. But no one has any doubts about this being a public party. In the elections of 2013 and 2018, PPP lost the elections except in Sindh. In Sindh, they formed the government for the 3rd time. After the success of the vote of no confidence against Prime Minister Imran Khan, PPP also joined the coalition government, and the Party Chairman Bilawal Zardari joined as Foreign M Though a number of steps were taken in this regard by the government led by Asif Ali Zardari which included but are not limited to, Employees Stock option scheme under which public sector employees were made share holders in their respective departments, free of cost housing scheme was initiated in Sindh under the name of Benazir Bhen Basti, more than 56,000 acres of land was distributed within the peasants, a comprehensive plan for the eradication of poverty was started under the name of Benazir Income Support Program which is now one of the largest social safety program in Asia. In addition to that a program named as waseela-e-haq was initiated under which 0.3 million rps. each were distributed in between thousands of deserving families so that they can start their own earning. Schemes such as Benazir life insurance scheme was also initiated. Thousands of contractual employees were not only regularized but thousand of other employees were also reinstated. As a result of these steps then President of Pakistan

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Mr. Asif Ali Zardari was elected as the Vice-President of the Socialist International.¹⁰ Key bills on female's rights were made current in National Assembly in 2009. The Federal government also administered the economic backing to females of household that decline under the poverty line. A female is provided Rs 3000 per month as supplementary income. The government earmarked Rs 70 billion in the year 2009 and 50 billion in the year 2010. The scheme benefited poor women of the country in both ways. First females were provided extra income. And secondly, they were certified and collected CNIC which was a cardinal for BISP as well as for voter registration process. These developments not only woke up Pakistani women to come to main stream politics but also compelled them to sense the feel of changing dynamics for their social and political realization. People's Party tried its best to establish good understanding with religious parties i.e. JUI was with the President Asif Ali Zardari, the Pakistan's biggest religious party, he reconstructed the Lal Masjid, did not insert any meaningless bump in front of religious parties, the Sunni Ittehad Council was involved in alliance and averted from any other exploit against the Madaras. The outrages with the religious parties were limited. Overall, religious parties were happy with the President Asif Ali Zardari.¹¹,

Conclusion

As considered liberal and secular party, PPP did not use the religious card in electoral democracy, the leadership constantly claimed as anti-establishment party and a competitor of right wing parties i.e. IJI or religious parties even PMLN. It is said that PPP government formed the culture of consistent politics and declared democracy as a best revenge. PPP invigorated parliamentary democracy. The PPP stands at an interesting juncture of time as a left wing party as a partner of PMLN in 2022. The two previous general elections in Pakistan (2013 and 2018) saw the PPP confined to Sindh due to its dismal electoral performance in other provinces. During the last two elections, however, it failed to garner a significant number of votes in Punjab. Since then, the PPP has been attempting to reorganize itself in Punjab. Indeed, if it can build on its roots in south Punjab, it could make a comeback. The party has a stronghold in the region, where it supports demands for a new province in the Siraiki-speaking districts of southern Punjab and, as a result of party patronage networks, enjoys the support of electoral heavyweights. In Sindh, the PPP, with its blend of ethnic nationalism, looks poised to continue its dominance within the province in the face of fragmented Sindhi nationalists as well as a divided MQM. Even if the PPP fails to capture power. Beyond street agitations, the party has intensified its contact with other opposition parties, with an eye on the 2023 general elections. The visit by Asif Ali Zardari and Bilawal Bhutto Zardari to Punjab reflects a renewed vigor for cooperation in the opposition ranks. Will Bilawal thrive on the inherited charisma of his grandfather? Will the PPP be able to accelerate its opposition in election 2023. The stage is set for an interesting display of oppositional politics by the PPP.

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